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Teaching Students of Higher Education Institutions to Utilize the Art of Public Speaking in Spiritual Activities during Classroom and Extracurricular Sessions

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***Abstract:** This article discusses issues related to improving the effectiveness of using the art of oratory in the process of spiritual and educational work in higher education institutions, speech activity, speech teaching, its significance and tasks, and the requirements for speech skills in the processes of spirituality and enlightenment.*

***Key words:** spirituality, enlightenment, word, emphasis, pronunciation, internal speech, external speech, communicative activity, mutual conversation, oratory, rhetoric, communication styles, sound, timbre, diction, articulation, rhythm.*

It is known that important aspects of the spiritual and educational development of society, the socio-spiritual perfection of the nation, go back to the art of oratory. Therefore, the rise of cultural and educational reforms in our country to the level of state policy, the improvement of our children's oratory skills, and the focus on issues of speech culture are becoming more relevant than ever, in our Republic, the laws "On the State Language," "On Education," the National Program for Personnel Training, and many other documents pay special attention to the issues of spiritual and educational upbringing. In order to express our thoughts in our native language independently, fluently, beautifully and concisely, we must have a sufficient level of speech culture and eloquence. Especially considering that the main tool of a teacher's work is their speech, mastering the art of oratory is one of the most important issues for students and teachers of all higher educational institutions. Particularly, the involvement of students in spiritual and educational events organized in higher education institutions and their preparation for these events is one of the forms of education in pedagogy. Employees of the spiritual and educational sphere (pro-rector, deans, zamekans, women's activists, tutors and youth leaders) in collaboration with students regularly organize such events on various directions and topics,

holidays or about the work and activities of the life path of great thinkers. Often, these events are hosted by students or faculty. Students are prepared for spiritual and educational activities for a certain period of time. However, it is precisely when they speak in public that they make mistakes due to excitement or fear. Not only students, but also teachers or leaders with a high level of knowledge and skills can make confusion in their speech due to intense excitement or various social reasons when they are given the opportunity to speak in public. This undermines the effectiveness of planned spiritual and educational events. They fail to achieve the desired result. To prevent such situations, it is necessary to instill in students knowledge about oratory during the lesson. Lessons are one of the main forms of education. During the lesson, a communicative connection arises between students and the teacher. Students learn new topics during the lesson. Solving specific problems and teaching oratory skills are carried out both in the classroom and in extracurricular activities at each individual time interval of the educational process. The lesson topic is the most important process for educating students as speakers. Accordingly, the system of academic disciplines, subject programs, should also have topics aimed at improving oratory skills. Students face the need to speak to the audience with a monologue, lecture, creative work, presentation, and defense. It should be noted that the advantage of the lesson as a form of organizing the pedagogical process lies in the fact that.

During the lesson, the student has the opportunity to speak to the audience:

1. The constant composition of students creates favorable conditions for the development of oratory skills.
2. Favorable conditions are created for combining frontal, group, and individual work, while students develop oratory skills.
3. The formation of abilities and skills allows the teacher to achieve cognitive development in a short period of time;

Despite its short duration, the lesson is a difficult and responsible stage of the learning process. The lesson develops basic speaking skills. It creates independent preparation for oratory in higher education institutions. One form of extracurricular work is a circle. It is advisable for every higher education institution to have clubs such as "Young Speakers," which contribute to the development of communication skills. The club develops creative activity, along with oratory, teaches students to learn literary language, to write stories, and poems. Prepares young speakers for speaking at correspondence events, spiritual and educational events, and meetings. It teaches them how to solve problems that become increasingly complex over time. The proper organization of research activities for students in higher education institutions, systematic and purposeful research activities, helps them to manifest themselves in all aspects. By enhancing the theoretical level of knowledge and developing practical skills, creativity develops both analytical and critical thinking, as well as cognitive activity and the ability to think. Expresses and defends their opinions. It develops the ability to successfully deliver speeches at events in higher education institutions. In the process of defending their work, students gain experience in oratory. Speaking skills are also formed in extracurricular activities, spiritual hours, various events, holidays, creative meetings, etc. A person differs from other beings in their knowledge of existence, their reason and experience, and their speech, and possesses wisdom and deep thinking with their reason. Science, on the other hand, is an important tool in human perfection, in achieving honor, and the thoughts and feelings, knowledge and culture, and level of each person are reflected in words, written and oral speech. In this way, people who are aware of the art of oratory and the ability to speak have long been valued in society as cultured intellectuals. Increasing the socio-pedagogical role of developing students' speaking skills in the process of spiritual and educational work helps to

unite young people based on the idea of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society" and to shape their worldview.

In conclusion, it is necessary to create conditions for students to become more familiar with the school of mastery of teachers when solving oratory problems. The meaning of the word "pedagogue" is that a child is a leader. The teacher is the leader, the student is the leader. Even an airplane that flies in the air has a special machine that can tow it. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a joint analysis of student broadcasts with recordings of the voices of famous speakers and actors, as well as their performance methods. There is not a single actor on the stage who has not followed or imitated someone. Given this, it is necessary to explain these phenomena to young students. The concepts of influence, repetition, and imitation are essential in their place. It would not be an exaggeration to say that we have orators who later acquired the skills of an orator by imitating someone. It should never be forgotten that the rhetoric platform is a platform that shows the power, power of influence, tenderness, wealth and beauty of language.

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